

**Κέντρο Ερευνών Αστρονομίας
και Εφαρμοσμένων Μαθηματικών**
της Ακαδημίας Αθηνών

Novel Features of the Pulsar Magnetosphere

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Hakobyan, Philippov & Spitkovsky (2023)

Hu & Beloborodov (2022)

Timokhin (2006)

Timokhin (2006)

The magnetosphere Y-point

$$L \approx \frac{\Omega^2 \Psi_{\text{open}}^2}{6\pi^2 c} \approx \frac{\Omega^2 B_*^2 r_*^6}{4cR_Y^2} = \frac{1}{x_Y^2} L_{\text{canonical}}$$

The magnetosphere Y-point

$$\rho_e \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B} = 0$$

$$(B^2 - E^2)_I = (B^2 - E^2)_{II}$$

$$E_p \equiv x B_p$$

$$(B_p)_I^2 = (B_p)_{II}^2 + \frac{B_{\phi II}^2}{1 - x^2} \neq 0$$

$$x \equiv R/R_{LC}$$

The magnetosphere Y-point

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The magnetosphere Y-point

Gourgouliatos &
Lynden-Bell (2019)

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Hu & Beloborodov (2022)

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Hu & Beloborodov (2022)

The magnetosphere Y-point

$$(B_p)_I^2 = \frac{B_{\phi II}^2}{1 - x^2}$$

Contopoulos, Ntotsikas
& Gourgouliatos
(in preparation)

The magnetosphere Y-point

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The pulsar magnetosphere with Machine Learning (PINN)